

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: AkzoNobel

Generating Biofilm Textures from
Optical Coherence Tomography Scans

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Contents

1	Executive summary	3
1.1	Background and data overview	3
1.2	Main objectives	4
1.3	Approach	4
1.4	Main Conclusions	5
1.5	Limitations	5
1.6	Recommendations and future work	6
2	Introduction	7
2.1	Marine fouling	7
2.2	Investigating fouling drag	8
2.3	Capturing biofilm textures with optical coherence tomography (OCT) imaging	8
2.4	Biofilm spatial heterogeneity over metre-scale spatial extents	10
3	Data	11
3.1	Overview	11
3.2	Data summary	12
3.3	Data visualisation	12
4	Methods	13
4.1	Data augmentation	13
4.2	Synthetic data generation	15
4.3	Fast Texture Synthesis using Tree-structured Vector Quantisation (FTS-TVQ)	17
4.4	Portilla-Simoncelli Texture Synthesis	18
4.5	Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)	21
4.6	Tiling for texture synthesis	23
5	Experiments	26
5.1	Results: Data augmentation	26
5.2	Results: Texture synthesis via PS-GAN	27
5.3	Results: Portilla-Simoncelli Texture Synthesis	27
5.4	Results: Fast Texture Synthesis using Tree-structured Vector Quantisation (FTS-TVQ)	28
5.5	Results: Comparative Evaluation of Model Performance	29

5.6	Results: Wang Tiling	30
6	Future work and research avenues	31
6.1	Image out-painting	31
6.2	Texture synthesis from a pixel and patch-based perspective	32
6.3	Texture synthesis using multiple images	32
6.4	Data augmentation for a generative adversarial network (GAN)	33
7	Conclusions	33
8	Team members	35
8.1	Participants	35
8.2	Problem Owners	36
8.3	Principal Investigators	36

1 Executive summary

1.1 Background and data overview

AkzoNobel is a global leading paints and coatings company, providing solutions to customers across a wide range of business segments from consumer goods to heavy industry (e.g. Oil and Gas and Marine industry). International Paint is a brand of AkzoNobel delivering paints/coatings solutions to the Marine, Yacht and Protective industry.

A major challenge for the marine industry is biofouling, the unwanted colonisation of marine/aquatic organisms on immersed substrates, which includes ship hulls. Biofouling on ships' hulls increases hull surface roughness, which in turn increases frictional resistance and ultimately increases fuel consumption and total emissions of a ship. A biofilm is a type of biofouling and is a slimy layer made of living microorganisms embedded in an extracellular polymeric matrix.

Biofilms on ships are known to increase the drag penalty by up to 40%. The degree to which a biofilm affects drag can be practically measured in hydrodynamic experiments - but such approaches require metre-scale sections of hull material (and biofilm) for testing purposes. As it is not practical to source large volumes of testing material directly, modern 3D printing technologies may offer an alternate solution, if these can accurately replicate sample materials and their surface properties.

Surveys of ships around the world show that, even visually, not all marine biofilms are the same. Variance in biofilms, attributed to differences in both the composition and community, results in differences to the frictional drag. Historically it was a real challenge to measure the surfaces of biofilms but more recently, biofilm imaging has opened up with the adoption of a technology called optical coherence tomography (OCT). OCT lets us image down through living biofilms over a surface area approximately the size of a penny.

Therefore, if practical drag measurements need metre-scale material samples, but OCT imagery can only provide centimetre-scale images, the open question for this project was to find a suitable methodology to replicate OCT textures at the metre-scale, potentially providing templates

for 3D printed hull sections suitable for hydrodynamic experiments [21].

The data available for the project was 36 sample OCT scans in the format of plain text files. Each file has the dimension 500x500 and depth values between 0 and 900, representing an elevation map covering 9mm x 9mm x 2.5mm biofilm.

1.2 Main objectives

AkzoNobel proposed the following challenge objectives:

1. Identify computational techniques that can be used to generate virtual biofilm elevation maps measured from real biofilms.
2. Test whether any of the identified techniques are able to generate artificial maps over larger spatial extents than those of the underlying real data, such as at a metre-scale, ship scale or infinitely.

1.3 Approach

1.3.1 Methods

Two strategies were presented in order to solve the challenge objectives.

The first challenge objective required identification of methods to generate new biofilm textures, with similar physical properties to the images provided. Three different methods were explored and compared:

1. Fast Texture Synthesis using Tree-structured Vector Quantisation (FTS-TVQ) [23]
2. The computational method of Portilla and Simoncelli [16]
3. Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [22]

The second challenge object required identification of methods, which can reproduce larger surface textures from the initial source images that retain the same metrics of interest. The Wang Tiles method was explored.

1.3.2 Data exploration and augmentation

Both the strategies shared two initial steps; data exploration and data augmentation.

Data exploration was undertaken to verify the properties of the raw dataset, and obtain the list of metrics of interest, such as roughness and depth of the images. In this step, visual analysis is recommended, plotting the distributions of such metrics, as well as 3D plots of the intensity maps. These metrics have been outlined in section [3.2](#).

Data augmentation was intended to increase the number of available data by making basic transformations of the original dataset. Due to time limitations, models could not be trained using the proposed data augmentation technique. However, it has been still described and recommended for future work. This step is covered in detail in section [4.1](#).

1.4 Main Conclusions

This project explored three approaches for at-scale elevation map generation: FTS-TVQ, Portilla-Simoncelli, and PS-GAN. The comparative performance of the Portilla-Simoncelli approach was the best of those tried in terms of mean square error (MSE) or mean percentage error (MPE) - though all approaches produced distributions of height values that were statistically significantly different from the original input texture.

For the second objective of scaling a small sample texture to a larger surface exhibiting the same topographical properties, we have explored the use of 'Wang Tiles' to generate, potentially arbitrarily large, texture images.

1.5 Limitations

The first limitation was that the provided dataset size was small, containing only 36 elevation maps. This was insufficient to train a deep generative model, such as PS-GAN, to have decent results.

The second limitation was that each model required a long time to train. This was especially true of the FTS-TVQ model, which takes three hours to process one sample image. Therefore, processing all 36 elevation maps proved prohibitive in terms of time and resource usage. Results as presented were based only a few of the sample images.

The third limitation are the possible deficiencies in the generalisability or external validity of the approaches outlined. This limitation is based on the provided dataset having a single source. All the 36 images belong to the same biofilm type, which means that any trained models may only be appropriate for that type, and not be representative for other types of biofilm.

1.6 Recommendations and future work

The problem of synthetic texture generation can be explored and analysed from different perspectives. There are multiple approaches for handling texture synthesis that could work better for this specific case, such as pixel or patch-based methods, where some algorithms have been proven useful for solving similar problems. Another possible direction could be to try image 'out-painting' strategies [24], although this would require to analyse the proposed challenge through a completely different lens. Image 'out painting' refers to extending an image beyond its original borders using a combination of the original image and generative AI.

A probable explanation of why the PS-GAN approach did not offer better results, could be due to the limited amount of training data. The strategy of data augmentation is considered a good practice for handling this problem, as a larger dataset could improve the obtained results by improving the generalisation ability of the model.

2 Introduction

2.1 Marine fouling

AkzoNobel is a multinational company that specialises in the production of paints and coatings for a wide range of industries, including aerospace, automotive, construction and marine industries. Sustainability and innovation is at the heart of AkzoNobel's ethos, investing in new technologies to develop solutions to help to safeguard our world far beyond tomorrow.

The challenge AkzoNobel is interested in relates to marine fouling. Marine fouling is the accumulation and growth of various organisms on submerged surfaces, such as the hulls of ships, boats, and other marine structures (see Figure 1). Organisms contributing to fouling can consist of macro-flora and fauna, such as barnacles, mussels, and seaweed, but also include biofilms – complex, organised communities of microorganisms attached to a surface and embedded in a protective matrix of polymer substances.

Figure 1: Marine fouling on a ship

Marine fouling can have a negative impact on the performance of a ship, increasing drag and reducing the speed and fuel efficiency of the vessel.

In addition, marine growth can sometimes cause corrosion and damage to the underlying structure. To prevent marine fouling, AkzoNobel produce a variety of paints and coatings, which deter the growth of fouling. To fully test the efficacy of coatings in resisting fouling, an understanding of the causes and variation of biofilm drag is required.

2.2 Investigating fouling drag

Biofilms can be considered as heterogeneous rough surfaces and their drag impact can be assessed in the hydrodynamics laboratory. Test pieces reflect the size of the instrumentation, and many hydrodynamics experimental systems (e.g. flow cells, tow tanks) require metre-scale panels. Larger test pieces are advantageous when assessing surfaces with spatial heterogeneity, but it is challenging to culture biofilms on such test pieces at scale and with adequate experimental replication.

Artificial surfaces which replicate the surface texture and spatial heterogeneity of living biofouling could provide an alternative testing route without the difficulties of maintaining biological cultures. Indeed, hydrodynamic testing of 3D-printed macrofouling has already been leveraged for executing precise hydrodynamic experimental designs [21].

For the case of biofilms, producing artificial test pieces requires:

1. measuring micron-scale surface texture and capturing these details as numerical meta data, e.g., summary statistics
2. using the meta data to produce suitable images with spatial heterogeneity over metre-scale extents.

2.3 Capturing biofilm textures with optical coherence tomography (OCT) imaging

The three-dimensional structure of biofilm fouling on fully immersed surfaces can be captured using an imaging technique called Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT). OCT uses interferometry and the scattering of low-coherence, long-wavelength light to produce sequential

Figure 2: Optical coherence tomography captures biofilm across sections (upper) which are assembled into three dimensional images (lower, with biofilm surface rendering).

cross-sectional images of biological materials which are collated into a three-dimensional image (Figure 2).

The instrument in use at AkzoNobel can image a volume of biofilm growth on a surface of approximately 90mm x 90mm x 2.5mm (length x width x depth) with a resolution on the order of ~ 10 microns. OCT is sometimes referred to as “meso-scale” imaging, in contrast to micro-scale confocal microscopy imaging. A single image of a biofilm volume, termed a ‘C-Scan’ is built up from numerous, two-dimensional elements, termed ‘B-scans’. Figure 2 is an example of how OCT captures B-sections in order to obtain the final intensity map in 3-D.

The water-biofilm interface and the biofilm-coating interface are identifiable in the 3D OCT images. After finding the two interfaces, it is possible to generate a biofilm elevation map for the sampled. Across different experiments, the variation and complexity of biofilm architectures

is readily apparent (Figure 2). Further examination suggests that many of these sample biofilms have characteristic textures with repetitive features.

Numerous quantitative spatial metrics can be calculated from these elevation maps, inclusive of traditional metrics common in the biofouling literature and considered relevant to frictional drag of fouled surfaces: average and maximum thickness, average roughness, and surface area coverage.

2.4 Biofilm spatial heterogeneity over metre-scale spatial extents

Quality OCT imaging carries a high cost, in that it is resource intensive to collect, analyse and store the images. A single high-quality C-scan file requires ~ 1 GB storage. To sequentially scan and then stitch together images across a single meter-scale test piece could require terabytes of disk space and many hours of instrument time. Meso-scale biofilm mapping by OCT is thus a process that is difficult to scale up.

At a lower resource cost, a biofilm elevation map covering a large spatial extent could be artificially generated using a simple tiling approach working from actual measurements. However, tiling introduces seams, which are themselves roughness features. The size of the tile and number of seams can be reduced by stitching multiple OCT images, reverting back to resource-intensive measurement.

Alternatively, AkzoNobel seeks to find a way to artificially generate a biofilm elevation map without resorting to tiling and instead by leveraging the information contained within a finite number of fields of view (elevation maps) of a given biofilm with a characteristic architecture.

3 Data

3.1 Overview

The primary data provided for the project were 36 text files, each containing 250,000 floating-point values. An individual file represents an OCT C-Scan with dimension (X-Y) of 500x500 pixels. The floating-point values give an elevation (Z) value ranging between 0 and 900.

Therefore, each file represents an elevation map covering a 9mm x 9mm x 2.5mm scan volume. Conversion to spatial units was therefore possible by applying the following conversion factors:

- x: 1 pixel = 0.018000 mm
- y: 1 pixel = 0.018000 mm
- z: 1 pixel = 0.002751 mm

In addition to the primary data, a metadata file was provided, summarising select, derived spatial properties of the individual files. These properties included:

- *ave_h_mm*: average z height [mm]
- *max_h_mm*: maximum z height [mm]
- *roughness_mm*: average of absolute difference between a given pixel's height and the average height.
- *sac*: percentage surface area coverage of the image where the height is greater than the specified thresholds@ 0.001, 0.005, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0 mm.
- *biovol_t*: total biovolume (average z height * surface area, mm³ = mg)
- *biovol_density*: total biovolume / surface area [mg/mm²]. NB: computationally identical to *ave_h_mm* but included to signpost historic comparisons.

3.2 Data summary

Table 1 summarises the properties of the dataset. Roughness is calculated as described in [4].

Metrics	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Height (depth)	0.4	0.2	0.0	2.0
Roughness	0.5	0.1	0.4	0.7
SAC 0.5	31.4	21.5	0.7	82.3
SAC 0.1	89.5	5.6	71.9	96.9
SAC 0.05	95.5	3.3	86.9	99.8

Table 1: Data summary from the 36 elevation maps.

In Table 1 Height (in mm) is the average intensity value of the images. Roughness (in mm) is the average of absolute difference between a given pixel's height and the average height. Surface area coverage (SAC) is the % coverage of the image where the height is greater than the specified threshold.

3.3 Data visualisation

The 3D plots of the data are shown in the millimetre (mm) scale, in which we multiply the original x and y by 0.018 and the Z by 0.002751. The thickness maps represent the depth of the biofilm, and it is clear that each elevation map has a vague pattern. This pattern becomes clearer when visualised on the corresponding 3D elevation map.

Figure 3: Illustration of two biofilm samples. The top-down thickness maps are obtained from OCT scans and the intensity indicates the thickness of each position. Visualising the thickness in 3D results in the 3D elevation map displayed in column 2. As these biofilm samples are from same group of biofilm, their thickness varies spatially but follows a similar distribution globally.

4 Methods

4.1 Data augmentation

Part of the challenge was the amount of the sample data available. Limited to 36 elevation maps, there was not enough sample data to apply machine learning methods.

Data augmentation is a possible solution to increase the quality and size of the training dataset, beyond an initial small number of samples. In data augmentation, slightly modified copies of the existing data are generated using a variety of different methods or transformations. By extending the training dataset, the risk of over-fitting can be reduced when training a machine learning model. Some of the strategies range from geometric transformations, feature space augmentation, kernel filters or generative adversarial networks, among others [1]. Although there are other

techniques that try to avoid over-fitting in Deep Learning, such as dropout or batch normalisation, data augmentation approaches the problem from the root, by expanding the training dataset [20].

In this project, a number of different data augmentation techniques have been identified, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Taxonomy of image data augmentations used in this project.

The main data augmentation strategy is based on basic image manipulation. Specifically, geometric transformations and kernel filters were used. As the orientation in space of the texture of each image was not considered relevant when considering the goal of extending given texture samples over a larger region, geometric transformations can be applied with great flexibility. The geometric transformations and kernel filters identified in this work are:

- Flipping: Horizontal and vertical axis flipping are one of the easiest transformations to implement. Furthermore, they have been proven useful on data-sets such as ImageNet [6].
- Zooming: This technique allows the obtaining of new images, based on patches extracted from sample images, whilst maintaining the same dimensions as the originals.
- Rotation: The image is rotated a specific angle between 1° and 359° , depending on the specifications.
- Gaussian filtering: Gaussian filtering blurs images by sliding a $n \times n$

matrix across the image. This action can improve the resistance to motion in the testing phase [1].

For conventional data augmentation techniques, if the augmentation is applied too frequently or aggressively on a small input dataset, or produces images too similar to the originals, then over-fitting may again be an issue, as the model may learn to recognise specific variations of the training data, rather than learning the underlying patterns [20]. Conventional data augmentation techniques may not always result in diverse enough data, particularly if the original data is already limited in terms of its variability. [1].

300 new samples were generated using these basic augmentations. In each iteration, the algorithm would select randomly a raw image and would apply a random subset of these transformations. The angle of rotation would be randomly selected from the set [0, 359] degrees, whereas the kernel size of the Gaussian Blur could be chosen among the values [5,7], and sigma had to be chosen from the set [1,2].

4.2 Synthetic data generation

This step aims to generate completely new textures with the same characteristics as the raw and augmented images, using various generative models. For synthetic data generation, several methods have been applied and compared. Note that the synthetic generation process differs from Data Augmentation, discussed in the previous section, which generates 'new' textures based on manipulation of the original sample images.

Contextually, we can divide the methods into two groups:

1. 'Classical' computer graphics methods, represented by the approaches FTS-TVQ and Portilla-Simoncelli.
2. Methods based on machine learning, typically involving neural networks, in this case Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs).

Texturing is a core process for computer graphics applications. The texturing process can be divided into three components: (1) texture acquisition, (2) texture mapping, and (3) texture rendering. Discussion of

how generated textures may be used in graphical applications is outside of the scope of this discussion.

The goal of texture synthesis can be stated as follows:

Given a texture sample, synthesise a new texture that, when perceived by a human observer, appears to be generated by the same underlying process (Figure 5).

The process of texture synthesis may be decomposed into two main components:

1. **Analysis:** Analysis relates to the estimation of the underlying generation process based on a given, finite set of texture samples. The estimation process should be able to model both the structural and stochastic parts of the input textures.
2. **Synthesis:** Synthesis involves a suitable methodology to take the parameters from the prior estimation process and create new textures using those data.

The overall success of synthetic generation may be determined either by the visual fidelity of the synthesised textures with respect to the original samples, or by a more rigorous approach, e.g. by statistical testing of estimation parameters derived from the original sample images against parameters calculated using the new, synthesised images.

The efficiency of the sampling procedure will directly determine the computational cost of texture generation. Essentially, texture synthesis algorithms differ in their specifics regarding the models used in the analysis part as well as the computations used in the synthesis part.

In this report, we concentrate on a narrow definition of textures, i.e. images containing repeating patterns. Since natural textures may contain interesting variations or imperfections, we also allow a certain amount of randomness over the repeating patterns. The amount of randomness can vary for different textures, from almost completely stochastic (e.g. grains on a sand beach) to almost completely deterministic (e.g. a man-made surface such as a tiled floor).

Example-based texture synthesis

Example-based texture synthesis [17] remains one of the most powerful

Figure 5: Texture synthesis: Given a sample texture, the goal is to synthesise a new texture that looks like the input. The synthesised texture is 'tileable' and can be of arbitrary size specified by the user.

methods as it works on a large variety of textures, is easy to use – the user only needs to supply an exemplar – and provides high output quality. In principle, the same process of providing exemplar textures, applies when building deep learning models. These, however, generally require a (very) large number of samples, in order to learn key features.

The end result of example-based texturing may be an arbitrarily large output texture that is visually similar to the exemplar(s) and does not contain any unnatural artefacts or repetition. The following two sub-sections will present a 'classic' computer graphics approach (FTS-TVQ)[23], followed by the Multi-Resolution Texture Synthesis [25] approach of Portilla and Simoncelli [16].

4.3 Fast Texture Synthesis using Tree-structured Vector Quantisation (FTS-TVQ)

Wei L. and Marc L. [23] developed a Fast Texture Synthesis algorithm based on Tree-structured Vector Quantisation (FTS-TVQ). This approach was derived from Markov Random Field (MRF) texture models. The synthesis is accelerated using tree-structure vector quantisation. Only

two inputs are needed, a texture patch (or image) and random noise with user-defined size. The algorithm modifies this random noise to make it look like the given example.

In a MRF method, a texture is modelled using both a *local* and a *stationary* random process, under the premise that each pixel has been characterised as a patch containing its neighbouring pixels. As the new texture is being generated pixel by pixel, the algorithm preserves the local similarity between the input texture and the output. In this context, the *local* property relates to the ability to predict each pixel using its neighbouring pixels, preserving its independence from the rest of the image; whereas the definition of *stationarity* stands for whether a portion of the image always appears similar when moving the viewing window through the texture.

The algorithm is instantiated by taking a sample image and an arbitrary noise image as input. To determine an output pixel value, its spatial neighbourhood (the L-shaped regions in red) is compared against all possible neighbourhoods from the input sample. The input pixel with the most similar neighbourhood is assigned to the output value. We use the sum of squared differences to measure the similarity between the neighbourhoods. The goal of this synthesis process is to ensure that the newly assigned pixel will maintain as much local similarity between the sample and the generated as possible. The same process is repeated for each output pixel until all the pixels are determined. Performance of the MRF method may be enhanced considerably using Tree-structured Vector Quantisation (TVQ) [23]. Vector quantisation is a lossy-compression method that decomposes an image down into a finite number of sub-regions bearing similar properties. Using a tree-based structure, such as a binary tree, provides a hierarchical ordering of the sub-regions, facilitating rapid processing.

4.4 Portilla-Simoncelli Texture Synthesis

The Portilla-Simoncelli texture model [16] is a computational model for analysing and synthesising images based on their textures. The methodology of the Portilla-Simoncelli texture model involves several key steps as shown in figure 7.

Figure 6: Illustration of the Fast Texture Synthesis using Tree-structured Vector Quantisation algorithm.

Figure 7: Illustration of Portilla-Simoncelli texture model [16] pipeline.

From figure 7, the model takes the homogeneous image as input and extracts multi-dimensional representations of the inputs via Gabor filter pyramids. Then the processed representations are then transformed into a set of features that capture information about the statistical properties of the texture components, including mean, standard deviation, skewness etc. Finally, the textures are combined with the representations to synthesise the outputs. In more detail the steps in the Portilla-Simoncelli process are:

1. Multi-resolution decomposition: The homogeneous image is decomposed into multiple band-pass filtered images, each containing texture information at a different scale. This is achieved using a series of filter banks that separate the image into different frequency bands.
2. Non-linear processing: Each band-pass filtered image is processed using a non-linear function that enhances the perceptual quality of the texture information. This is achieved using a local contrast normalisation algorithm that amplifies the local contrast of the image while preserving its global 'energy'.
3. Statistics computation: The statistical properties of each band-pass filtered and processed image are computed using a set of filter banks that extract various texture features, such as local orientation and texture energy.
4. Encoding and analysis: The texture features are encoded into a set of parameters that capture the salient properties of the texture information. These parameters are then used to analyse the texture information and to synthesise new textures.
5. Synthesis: New textures are synthesised by generating random noise that matches the statistical properties of the original image's texture features. The synthesised textures are then combined into a single image using a multi-resolution synthesis algorithm.

The Portilla-Simoncelli texture model has been shown to be effective in a wide range of image-processing tasks, including texture segmentation, texture classification, and texture synthesis. However, to achieve the best performance, it always requires an instance-wise choice of hyper-parameters. The recursive process used by the algorithm can be

Figure 8: Illustration of the GAN architecture. The generator 'G' takes noise z as input and attempts to generate samples that are similar to the real sample x in order to fool the discriminator 'D'

computationally intensive, being sensitive to increases in input resolution.

4.5 Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), first introduced by Goodfellow *et al.* [10], are a machine learning technique able to generate new data that presents the same statistics as the training dataset. The GAN architecture is composed of a generative model 'G', that attempts to learn the training data's distribution, and a discriminator 'D', that attempts to identify generated output from training data (Figure 8). The central idea in training 'G' and 'D' of GANs is inspired by game theory: 'G' tries to fool 'D' into classifying a generated output as a training input, whereas 'D' attempts to distinguish generated output from training input. Over time, 'G' generates output that gets closer to the training input data distribution [22].

DeepTextures [9] is a GAN that was first applied as a parametric model for texture synthesis. The model has shown improvement to previous parametric model-based texture synthesis. However, its use of iterative back-propagation is costly in both computational time and memory. Spatial GAN (S-GAN) [12] extends the input noise from a single vector to a whole spatial tensor and utilises a modified Deep Convolutional GAN (DC-GAN) [18] architecture, employing convolutional networks rather than fully connected layers. As a result, S-GAN is able to create any desired output texture size. However, the limitations of DeepTextures and

Figure 9: PS-GAN architecture. Adapted from Bergmann *et al.* [2].

S-GAN is that they are limited to stationary, ergodic, and stochastic textures, i.e. they are not able to capture long-range correlations.

Periodic Spatial GAN (PS-GAN) is able to capture long-range correlations in images by constructing the input noise tensor with three components [2], shown in Figure 9. (1) The local independent part d^l , is sampled from its statistical model to allow the generation of spatial variance and diversity. (2) the spatial global part d^g , is a random patch selection from d^l and represents the learned textures of the PS-GAN. (3) The periodic part d^p , takes the random patch d^l and puts it through a multi-layer perceptron to allow learning of the periodic pattern from the global captures.

The generator 'G' maps the input noise tensor to an input image. To capture long-range correlations of textures, the input noise tensor is composed d^g , d^l , and d^p . The discriminator 'D' then attempts to distinguish the generated data from the training data.

4.6 Tiling for texture synthesis

Texture synthesis can be defined as the process of enlarging an image by taking into account its structural content in the procedure. Some of the considerations when synthesising a texture are:

- the final output size should be user selectable.
- the output should preserve the basic structural content of the raw image.
- artefacts such as sharp edges or texture blocks should be avoided.
- the output should avoid repetitive textures if necessary.

There are different approaches in order to synthesise a texture, such as tiling, stochastic texture synthesis, chaos mosaic, pixel-based texture synthesis, patch-based texture synthesis or Deep Learning and Neural Network approaches.

Previous sections in this report have discussed a variety of ways to perform texture synthesis to produce images of a similar or identical resolution to a training set of initial, sample images. This section focuses on the use of a tiling strategy to expand a smaller, initial image into a coherent image of far larger resolution. A tiling strategy was studied as a first and exploratory approach due to its simplicity and time constraints associated to the nature of this project.

Tiling, simply put, consists of copying and pasting the same image side-by-side over the entire area to be covered. Nevertheless, this often results in repetitive patterns that do not represent the complexity of the texture.

Wang Tiles [5] is a stochastic algorithm that allows an image to be tiled non-periodically, covering large areas with a pattern, but avoiding periodic artefacts. Wang Tiles were first used in texture synthesis by Stam [11]. A Wang Tile can be defined as a small, square tile whose edges are colour-coded.

Cohen *et al.* [5] introduced a stochastic process for placing the individual tiles. This algorithm uses a set of tiles that will be different from each other depending on the colour of their edges. An example of a subset of Wang tiles is shown in Figure 10. This algorithm is based on the assumption that

the new synthetic texture can grow from West (W) to East (E) and from North (N) to South (S) by following the next steps:

1. Select a random tile from the set of possible tiles, and place it in the NW position of the layout (Step 1 in Figure 10).
2. Grow the texture to the right by selecting a new tile whose W edge can match the E edge of the tile on its left (Step 2 of Figure 10).
3. Grow the texture downwards by selecting a new tile whose N edge can match the S edge of the tile upwards (Step 3 of Figure 10).
4. Continue by randomly selecting those tiles which N and W edges match the S and E edges of the adjacent tiles, until covering all the extension (Final Result of Figure 10).

When this algorithm is applied to real textures, the set of tiles is created using patches, also called samples, of the input image. The user specifies the number of random samples to obtain from the input image. Some of these samples (up to four at one time) are fitted in a diamond shape, as shown in Figure 11. In order to merge these samples, the algorithm optimises the cutting paths. Samples can only be merged as long as the difference in pixel intensities at the boundaries is below a threshold. Thus, the combined samples in this diamond shape are cut along the diagonals, obtaining a tile. This tile is the square represented in the image a) in Figure 11. As the same sample is used for all tiles sharing an edge colour, the tiles will always fit together, avoiding sharp edges in the synthesised texture.

Figure 10: Wang Tiles algorithm. step 1) random selection of a tile (tile a); step 2) selection of tile b whose red W edge matches the red E edge of tile a ; step 3) selection of tile g whose green N edge matches the green S edge of tile a . The final result image has been obtained from Cohen *et al.* [5].

Figure 11: Process for fitting small patches from the input image into a diamond shape and how to create the square tile from the diamond shape. a) Four patches from the input texture combined to form a diamond geometry; b) example of 8 valid sets for further creation of Wang Tiles. Figure obtained from Cohen *et al.* [5].

5 Experiments

5.1 Results: Data augmentation

Ultimately, the data augmentation strategy, outlined in section 4.1, was not used for increasing the training dataset size. However, a pipeline implementing this strategy was created, and some results are shown in Figure 12. Random rotation, random flipping, random zoom and Gaussian blur with random parameters were the transformations applied to our images.

Figure 12: Illustration of data augmentation. To extend the existing dataset to meet the training quantity needs, we augmented the original image with affine transformations, random crop and Gaussian morphing.

5.2 Results: Texture synthesis via PS-GAN

Figure 13 shows the outcomes of the PS-GAN. The generated image is very blurry with no detail similar to the original data present. Furthermore, the distribution of the heights is not completely dissimilar but lacking a clear peak and is not gamma distributed. The roughness distribution however, shows that whilst the means of the generated and actual distributions are similar, the original data has a much larger variance than the generated data.

Figure 13: Results of the PS-GAN. Left: an example image. Middle: a plot of the distributions of the generated heights compared to the original images. Right: a plot of the distributions of the generated roughness compared to the original images.

5.3 Results: Portilla-Simoncelli Texture Synthesis

Figure 14 gives the outcomes of the Portilla-Simoncelli model. Visually, the images generated by this model appear similar to the originals in pattern, repetitiveness, and texture. The distribution of the heights are very similar, almost perfectly overlapping.

The only distinct differences are where the original images show small 'bumps'. The original images have bumps at zero from when all negative depths were set to zero in the pre-processing phase, which the generated data has exacerbated into a distinct peak. The original data also shows a small bump in its peak which the generated data has smoothed. For the

Figure 14: Results of the Portilla and Simoncelli model. Left: an example image. Middle: a plot of the distributions of the generated heights compared to the original images. Right: a plot of the distributions of the generated roughness compared to the original images.

roughness however, the distributions are almost perfect, with the original data only having a slightly higher average.

5.4 Results: Fast Texture Synthesis using Tree-structured Vector Quantisation (FTS-TVQ)

Due to time constraints, the FTS-TVQ model was only able to produce one image, which is shown in Figure 15. This means that it is not possible to compare the spread of the depths or the roughness of this model to the originals, but the generated image appears to be of a high quality. Similar to the Portilla and Simoncelli model, it has patterns, repetitiveness, and texture that would be expected from the generated data. The further outcomes of this and the other two models are reported in Tables 2 and 3.

Figure 15: The image generated by the FTS-TVQ model.

5.5 Results: Comparative Evaluation of Model Performance

This section examines the performance of the three selected texture synthesis methods against an actual texture sample, in terms of both derived error and performance metrics, as well as select values of physical characteristics.

Methods	MSE	MPE(%)	Runtime (test)	p-value
FTS-TVQ	429.4	128.5	3 hours	0
Portilla and Simoncelli	1.9	16.8	20 secs	0
PSGAN	83.0	133.1	2 minutes	0

Table 2: Model evaluation - Performance and error metrics

In Table 2 MSE is the mean-square error between the generated values and the ground truth regarding roughness, height, and SAC measurements. Similarly, MPE is the mean percentage error. Run-time (test) is the time taken for a model to generate one elevation map. The P-value is the p-value we obtained after running a Mann-Whitney test against a null hypothesis that there is no difference between the sample height distribution and modelled height distribution.

Based on the results, the Portilla and Simoncelli approach has the lowest MSE and MPE. The method is also the quickest to generate elevation maps. In contrast, FTS-TVQ has the greatest MSE and is time-consuming to run. Furthermore, the Mann-Whitney test p-values for those models are 0, indicating that the distributions of the data we generated significantly differ from the original data, even though the 2D plots appear very similar.

Methods	Roughness	Height	Max height	SAC 0.5	SAC 0.1	SAC 0.05
Original data	0.5	0.4	2.0	31.4	89.5	95.5
FTS-TVQ	0.4	0.9	1.7	82.9	99.9	100.0
Portilla and Simoncelli	0.5	0.4	0.8	30.9	89.1	94.6
PSGAN	0.5	0.5	1.5	42.3	94.8	99.2

Table 3: Results of each model with the main features

Table 3 gives the results of the main features used to compare the generated images to the originals. Overall, all models returned a mean roughness similar to the original images but the other features show more separation. The Portilla-Simoncelli model was the most accurate, with only the maximum height differing significantly from the target. The PS-GAN and FTS-TVQ models differed from the target for most features. Notably, the FTS-TVQ model returned a much higher mean height and SAC0.5 than the originals and other models.

5.6 Results: Wang Tiling

Figure 16 presents a large, high resolution texture generated using the Wang Tiles procedure. The generated texture is visually similar to the original, smaller input texture -though a certain amount of similarities in visible structure patterns are discernible as artefacts of the tiling process. The larger image also has similar calculated mathematical properties to its input counterpart.

Figure 16: The result of the Wang Tiles algorithm.

6 Future work and research avenues

Based on the limitations of the small sample size of the biofilm dataset provided, the limitations of outputs produced over the period of the Study Group and literature identified during the course of the Study Group, but not followed up on due to time constraints, avenues for future work include:

- Thinking from image out-painting direction
- Texture synthesis from a pixel and patch-based perspective
- Texture synthesis using multiple images as input
- Data augmentation for a generative adversarial network

6.1 Image out-painting

Image out-painting [24], also known as image extrapolation, is a computer vision task that aims to generate plausible content outside the boundaries of an input image. Unlike image in-painting [3], which fills in missing or damaged parts of an image, out-painting generates new content beyond the visible boundaries of the image. This task has various practical

applications, including generating realistic backgrounds for images or videos, expanding the field of view of cameras, and creating immersive virtual reality environments. At present a 'cutting-edge' approach may use text prompts as input to a generative AI such as DALL-E.[14].

Image out-painting can be challenging due to the uncertainty of the content that lies outside the image boundaries. Therefore, recent approaches rely on learning-based methods, particularly deep neural networks, to generate the missing content. However, unlike the vast variations associated with generating a full range of natural images, biofilm images are likely to be more homogeneous, even across larger scales. Therefore it is considered that the out-painting approach is a promising avenue for exploration, if the volume of training data can be increased. Additionally the out-painting algorithm can achieve larger scale outputs in a single process, alleviating the additional difficulties associated with multi-stage processing.

6.2 Texture synthesis from a pixel and patch-based perspective

Although the Wang Tiles [5] procedure has shown promising results, there are other texture synthesis algorithms that can be explored and that have proven satisfactory results in solving similar problems. Pixel-based texture synthesis strategies are based on copying one pixel at a time, being able to synthesise from regular to stochastic textures [19]. Some algorithms use Markov fields [15], image analogies, tree-structured vector quantisation [23] or non-parametric sampling [7]. One of the main problems is that they usually show visual artefacts related to blurred features during the texture expansion [19]. One solution to this problem is using patch-based methods, which work with patches of neighbouring pixels. Some of the most used strategies based on this concept are 'image quilting' [8] and 'graphcut' textures [13].

6.3 Texture synthesis using multiple images

The Wang Tiles [5] procedure is able to synthesise a texture using only one image as input. However, as only a single image is used, any deficiencies inherent in that image will be carried over into the larger

texture. For example using the Wang Tiles procedure with an input image exhibiting less height variability than the actual target sample will result in a larger synthesised texture exhibiting the same lack in height variability. This is why it is worth exploring other texture synthesis or tiling methods that could use actual physical descriptors of the required surface, or multiple textures, as direct inputs, in order to generate a final synthesised texture, The Wang Tiles algorithm will only produce good results when the input texture sample already possesses the desired surface characteristics.

6.4 Data augmentation for a generative adversarial network (GAN)

Although Data Augmentation strategies have been partially covered in this report, this strategy was not used to train any Deep Learning model during the project due to time constraints. Considering these images to train a GAN model should improve the results obtained by this method.

7 Conclusions

In this project, we have examined two challenges regarding the generation of synthetic texture maps, based on OCT scans, as 'proofs-of-concept'.

The first challenge was, 'how to generate synthetic textures from exemplar scan images at a similar resolution to the originals, bearing equivalent statistical properties' and the second challenge was 'how to generate larger scale images from a pool of smaller images, without undesirable features, such as obvious seams, occurring'.

For the first challenge, we explored three approaches for at-scale elevation map generation:

- Periodic Spatial - Generative Adversarial Networks (PS-GAN).
- Portilla and Simoncelli's computational method.
- Fast Texture Synthesis using Tree-Structured Quantisation (FTS-TVQ).

We have found that the Portilla-Simoncelli approach performed the best out of all of the above, based on both visual inspection (Figure 14) and examination of performance and error metrics (Section 5.5).

For the second issue of large image synthesis from a small sample texture, we explored the use of 'Wang Tiles'. By visual comparison, the resulting sample (Figure 16) included repeated patterns that differ from the original data. However, this method has the potential to generate texture data on a larger scale.

8 Team members

8.1 Participants

Genevieve Moat is a PhD student from the school of computing at Newcastle University. Their research is focused on building a automatic tool to recognise primate's postural behaviour and facial expression. They acted as the facilitator, ensuring smooth project delivery, as well as the implementation of the PS-GAN model, and in contributing to the writing of this report.

Chloe Hinchliffe Contributed to this DSG by analysing the measures and distributions of these original and generated data, and assessing the quality of the generated data.

Hanz Tantiangco is a PhD student in the Information School at the University of Sheffield. Their research interests are in deep learning and chemo-informatics, specifically *de novo* design. They contributed to the project by working on the GAN modelling, and in contributing to the writing of this report.

Knectt Paulschoh Lendoye L'eyebe is a PhD candidate in the School of Computing, Newcastle University, with interest in analysing bio-markers responsible for diseases affecting vision and the neural system. His contribution to this DSG was in the implementation of the Fast Texture Synthesis algorithm to generate synthetic biofilms images.

Ning Bi is a PGR student from the School of Computing, University of Leeds. Their doctoral research is about CVDs motion modelling, anatomical structure analysis, and abnormality detection. Their research interests include, but are not limited to, Computer Vision, Medical Image Analysis, Variational Models, and Sequential data analysis. They contributed to this DSG in implementation of the various compared methods, in debugging, providing illustrations, and in contributing to the writing of this report.

Sofia Sorbet Santiago is a PhD student in the Translational and Clinical Research Institute in Newcastle University. Their PhD is focused on bioinformatics, processing clinical data to find biological paths of immunological diseases. Their interests include bio-informatics,

bio-statistics and Machine Learning methods applied to health data sets. They contributed to this DSG by creating the data augmentation pipeline and contributing to the writing of this report.

8.2 Problem Owners

Marie Dale is a Research Scientist working in the Fouling Control R&D Team at AkzoNobel with a technical focus on marine biofouling identification and ecology.

Jennifer Longyear is a Research Scientist at AkzoNobel with a technical focus on quantification of marine biofouling and its hydrodynamic consequences.

8.3 Principal Investigators

Louise Braithwaite is a data scientist at the National Innovation Centre for Data. She completed an MSc in Data Science at Newcastle University in 2020. Her technical background is in exploratory data analysis and data visualisation.

Paul Goodman is a data scientist at the National Innovation Centre for Data. Previously they have been employed as Lecturer in Intelligent Transport Systems at Newcastle University, and a Post-Doctoral Researcher in Transport Systems and the Environment at Newcastle University and the University of Leeds.

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